

Need of Studying Social Awareness Among Young Individuals for Social Entrepreneurship: Evidence from West Bengal

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Abstract

An apparently contrasting viewpoint in entrepreneurship is the term social entrepreneurship. While commercial entrepreneurship represents the identification, evaluation, and exploitation of opportunities that result in profits, social entrepreneurship, in contrast, refers to the identification, evaluation, and exploitation of opportunities that result in social value. In the context of social value, social entrepreneurship is crucial for teenagers as it fosters both understanding and informed decision-making in diverse social contexts, and helps them to develop their ability to be part of social movements often going beyond the realms of social entrepreneurship. International studies have examined social awareness and its components - such as gender, racial, religious, and political awareness - across various age groups, focusing primarily on race, gender, region, and sometimes education level. On a national scale, such studies have primarily undertaken in rural areas, examining social awareness directly or indirectly. Some studies show disparities in awareness across gender, caste, religion, region, and family status, while others claim no significant difference. Under this backdrop, the current researchers aim to study social awareness among the young people from different social aspects. Our study utilizes data collected through a survey by the Jana Sanskriti team under the Azim Premji Philanthropic Initiative, focusing on some areas of South 24 Parganas and Purulia districts of West Bengal due to prior rapport building there with the locals. Our findings suggest that there is disparity in social awareness among the youths across their gender, caste, region, age, and education, though no disparity across religion was detected. These outputs of the study will not only be useful from the perspective of social entrepreneurship, but also from the point of view of the policy-makers at any level. We recommend educating the groups with relatively low awareness, an effort that Jana Sanskriti(<https://janasanskriti.org/>) is advancing through the use of theatre and plays.

Key words: Commercial Entrepreneurship, Social Entrepreneurship, Social Awareness

1 Introduction

Entrepreneurship as stated by [1] is the core force of economic growth; the economic development which one experiences is just due the prevailing force of entrepreneurship. The entrepreneurship has many other types as well; it is divided on different traits and criteria, one of the criteria being Social. This type of entrepreneurship is very unique in nature and has different blends of components. The prime objective of social entrepreneurship stands different

than the usual objectives of entrepreneurship; here social benefits are clubbed with economic benefits. Most of the times, social entrepreneurship is used in synonymous with social service/work. Social entrepreneurship as a practice that integrates economic and social value creation has a long heritage and a global presence [2]. The concept of social entrepreneurship means different things to different people and researchers [3]. One group of researchers refers to social entrepreneurship as not-for-profit initiatives in search of alternative funding strategies, or management schemes to create social value [4], [5]. A second group of researchers understands it as the socially responsible practice of commercial businesses engaged in cross sector partnerships [6], [7]. And a third group views social entrepreneurship as a means to alleviate social problems and catalyze social transformation [8].

Social entrepreneurship takes various forms based on its objectives. It includes the for-profit sector, where social-purpose ventures combine profit-making with addressing societal challenges [9],[10] (Dees & Anderson, 2003; Emerson & Twersky, 1996), and corporate social entrepreneurship, where businesses align social impact with strategic goals [4](Austin, Leonard, Reficco, & Wei-Skillern, 2004). The non-profit sector [3](Dees, 1998) focuses solely on social value creation, as seen in initiatives like Jana-Sanskriti . Additionally,(Dees, 1998)[3] hybrid models blend for-profit and non-profit approaches, addressing social needs while ensuring financial sustainability.

The social activities of Jana-Sanskriti align with the non-profit sector, focusing on social value creation. Before initiating social entrepreneurial activities in any area, it is essential to understand the local social dynamics, including fostering social awareness among youth, particularly those in high school and college. Social awareness involves not just meeting basic needs - such as food, water, shelter, healthcare, and education - but also enhancing intellectual capacities. It enables individuals to comprehend and empathize with others' emotions, perspectives, and social cues, promoting meaningful interactions. Fostering social awareness among youth is crucial, as it encourages informed decision-making, enables participation in social movements beyond entrepreneurship, and equips them to contribute positively to their communities. This involvement strengthens social cohesion and personal growth, playing a vital role in the success of community-driven projects.

Awareness among people as stated by [11] plays an important role in carrying out their functions and adapting to live in multi-cultural contexts from their early age to the maturity. [12] studied the reality of social awareness and responsible decision making of grade 4 and 5 students in Vietnam and the correlation between these two. It deployed similar questionnaires with a 3-point Likert scale and performed One-Way ANOVA to examine the disparity in awareness levels by gender and residential area, and also used Pearson's Correlation Coefficient to study the relationship between social awareness and responsible decision-making. The results indicated that the social awareness among individuals is average while responsible decision-making ability is slightly above average. Another study [13] delves into the political awareness among university students in post-apartheid South Africa. It utilized Ordinary Least Squares Regression to study the relationship between political awareness and off-campus political activity also studying the correlation between Off-Campus Political Participation and different other variables like sex, age, faculty of study and year of study. It found that the effect of political awareness was significant on off-campus political activity and the only variable with statistically significant effect on political awareness and off campus activity was year of study. Another study [14] examined the relationship between inter group dialogues and adolescents' ethnic-racial identity and racism awareness using similar statistical tests like ANOVA and post-hoc tests. The findings indicated that there were statistically significant ethnic-racial group differences in ethnic-racial identity, but no group differences in racism awareness were found.

The study of social awareness among students has been approached from various an-gles in India. One notable study [15] conducted a gender-based comparative analysis of reading habits among undergraduate students, emphasizing the importance of systematic reading in intellectual and social development. This study utilized One-Way ANOVA to analyze the reading materials preferred by male and female students, aiming to uncover any gender

disparities in reading habits eventually finding no significant difference among the two genders. Another significant contribution [16] explored students' awareness of human rights education at the higher secondary school level, primarily employing qualitative methods and relying on descriptive analysis. A third relevant study [17] conducted a comparative analysis similar to the second paper but focused on gender differences in human rights awareness. A major study done in this field on West Ben-gal is [18]. Very similar to our study, it adopts a questionnaire feedback-based analysis technique with twenty questions on a five-point Likert scale with the options "Strongly Agree", "Agree", "Neutral", "Disagree" and "Strongly Disagree" making up the questionnaire. The area of study for this paper was Purba Medinipur and the candidates were 100 school students. It utilized t-test and found disparity across different variables of study.

Existing literature shows that many similar studies in this domain, including those focused on West Bengal, often have limited sample sizes or lack quantitative depth. For instance, [18] had only 100 samples with 20 questions and did not perform normality tests to justify parametric methods. Additionally, the study involved only three variables, which did not fully utilize the sample data.

A more formal definition states: Social entrepreneurship is the innovative, social value creating activity that can occur within or across the nonprofit, business, or government sectors. Such social value, therefore, may have little to do with profits but may rather involve the fulfillment of the basic and long-standing needs such as providing food, water, shelter, medical services, and other social supports to those members of society who are in need, as also to enhance their intellectual capacities. The last mentioned is particularly important since the success of social entrepreneurship definitely depends on a team of dedicated individuals particularly belonging to the class of the deprived section who would have to be strongly socially aware. So, what is social awareness? It is the ability to comprehend and empathize with other's; perspectives, emotions, and social cues, and to effectively apply this understanding in the interactions with them. This faculty is crucial for studying social awareness of teenagers as it fosters both understanding and informed decision-making in diverse social contexts, and helps them to develop their ability to be part of social movements often going beyond the realms of social entrepreneurship. It equips them to navigate and contribute positively to their communities, promoting social cohesion and personal development, thus contributing immensely to the society successfully.

The survey by Jana Sanskriti investigates combined awareness on caste-ism, patriarchy, and political dynamics in rural West Bengal's South 24 Parganas and Purulia districts among adolescents aged 12 to 21. This area of study was chosen for our study because of prior rapport building and accessibility. The survey was conducted at the KKB Centre under the APPI project. Our paper investigates the impact of demographic and societal variables such as race, gender, region, and age on social awareness levels. Utilizing statistical tests on responses from 406 participants to a comprehensive 64-question survey (post pre-processing) across four categories (gender, caste, religion, and politics), we aim to provide a robust analysis. By examining seven key covariates, our study offers a rigorous assessment of disparities among different groups and sections.

2 Hypotheses

The central objective of this analysis is to evaluate a comprehensive set of null hypotheses positing that social awareness - as measured comprehensively across all items in the administered questionnaire - is uniformly distributed across key demographic and geographic strata. Specifically, the framework formally tests the baseline assumption that there are no statistically significant disparities in social awareness levels attributable to individual characteristics such as age, gender, and educational attainment. Furthermore, it examines the premise of strict homogeneity across broader socio-cultural and spatial dimensions, testing for a lack of variance in social awareness based on racial classification, religious affiliation, localized residential block, or broader district geography.

3 Study Area and Data Collection

The area of South 24 Parganas and Purulia was chosen due to prior rapport building and high accessibility to the target population in the study areas.

The survey was developed based on extensive field experience and academic input from the Indian Statistical Institute. The Jana Sanskriti team, with over 40 years of field engagement, designed the survey to capture societal beliefs using a Likert-scale response format with options “not right at all”, “not right”, “don’t know” and “totally right”.

Participants independently completed the survey, with trained enumerators available for clarification. The survey had 458 respondents, ensuring a comprehensive representation of the population.

The survey was designed over one month and administered over two months in South 24 Parganas and Purulia through a structured questionnaire having 64 question items covering several social aspects and responses were graded on a scale from 1 (most negative) to 5 (most positive). Thus, the study had covered 405 adolescents aged 12 to 21.

4 Analysis Technique

First, total scores for each candidate were calculated and standardized. Normality of the total score distribution was assessed using the Kolmogorov-Smirnov test and normality was confirmed. A deterministic technique was applied to categorize achievement level of the candidates into three groups / categories based on mean (μ) and standard deviation (σ) of their total scores: below average, average, and above average. Candidates with total scores below ($\mu - \sigma$) were categorized as below average, those with scores between ($\mu - \sigma$) and ($\mu + \sigma$) were categorized as average, and those with scores above ($\mu + \sigma$) were categorized as above average. Its theoretical aspects and comparison with the actual histogram with density of the normalized scores is depicted below in Figure 1.

Figure 1: Normal Curve v/s Histogram of Normalized Total Scores

Under each categorical variable, the percentage of people in these three categories was observed.

Since, the total scores follow normal distribution, one-way ANOVA was used to test the hypotheses as mentioned above. To address highly imbalanced sample sizes, particularly when the minority group was small, we utilized an iterative stratified down sampling technique on the majority group, followed by Welch's t-test to account for unequal variances.

5 Results

5.1 Demographic Features of Survey

The gender composition reveals a majority of females (73.4%) compared to males (26.6%). This can be attributed to Jana Sanskriti's predominantly female-oriented initiatives. Figure 2 also suggests it. The survey respondents are primarily from KKB, thus the gender participation rate in the children's workshop is also mirrored in the analyzed data.

Figure 2: Gender And Religion Pie Charts

The collected data pertains to a religious composition, with 93.4% being Hindus, 4.6% Muslims, 2% belonging to other religions as illustrated in Figure 1, and a category of individuals who prefer not to disclose their religious affiliation.

Figure 3: Region and Race Pie Charts

In terms of region, the data shows distribution as follows: Pathar Pratima - 43.3%, Kulpi - 25.6%, Pancha - 20.4%, Hura - 8.3%, and Manbazar - 2.4%. These regions are the primary areas of focus for Jana Sanskriti’s activities as illustrated in figure 3.

In the categorical breakdown of respondent castes, the distribution is as follows: SC -33%, General - 27.3%, OBC - 22.9%, ST - 9.7%, and 6.4% preferred not to respond. This diverse caste composition highlights the emphasis of Jana Sanskriti on inclusive participation from individuals belonging to various communities in their sessions. Once again it is demonstrated by figure 3.

We have examined the educational classes in which these respondents are enrolled, particularly within the context of KKB where the survey was conducted. KKB’s core emphasis lies in imparting diverse art forms to adolescents and children, with the aim of nurturing them into well-informed and conscientious citizens. As a result, the survey results reveal a significant majority of respondents falling within the educational range of classes 8 to 12. Most of the age group belongs to the 15-18 age category. The figure 4 demonstrates it.

Figure 4: Age and Education Pie Charts

The survey inquiries revolve around four primary dimensions: caste, gender, religion, and political ideology. The distribution of questions is slightly varied, with caste and gender carrying greater significance, while religion and political ideology follow suit. The survey’s structure is thoughtfully crafted to comprehensively capture opinions across the dataset. We can refer to figure 5.

Figure 5: Questions Divisions Pie Chart

5.2 Achievement Level by Deterministic Approach

After cleaning the data, 404 candidates are finally considered for studying their awareness level on the basis of total score which approximately follows normal distribution (using normality test procedure Kolmogorov - Smirnov at level of 0.053) with estimated mean ($\mu = 217.69$) and standard deviation ($\sigma = 21.70$). On total score, all the candidates have been categorized into three groups — below average, average, and above average as described below:

1. **Below Average:** Candidates whose scores are below ($\mu - \sigma = 195.99$)
2. **Average:** Candidates whose scores fall between ($\mu - \sigma = 195.99$) and ($\mu + \sigma = 239.39$).
3. **Above Average:** Candidates whose scores are above ($\mu + \sigma = 239.39$).

Then, across the three categories, the percentage distributions are obtained by district, blocks, age, sex, religions, race and education (All tables in Github Repository) from which the following findings are observed. It shows that when two districts combined, i.e., overall awareness level at neither below average (16.8%) nor above average (17.8%) is much, whereas majority (65.3%) is at average. When district-wise distribution is gone through, it illustrates that South 24 Parganas has a higher percentage of above average (21.4 %) and average (66.8 %) scores compared to Purulia (9.7 % and 62.1 % respectively). In case of block-wise distribution, it is observed that Pathar Pratima has the highest percentage of above average scores (22.6 %). Regarding religion, it indicates that Hindus and Muslims show different patterns in social awareness, with Muslims (30 %) having a higher percentage of above average scores compared to Hindus (17.2 %), though the sample size for Muslims is significantly smaller. The gender-wise distribution shows that females have a higher percentage of above average (20.9 %) and average scores (67.6 %) compared to males (9.3 % and 59.3 % respectively) in case of both districts, indicating higher social awareness among the females. The distribution by race shows that the General category has the highest percentage of above average scores (22.8%), while the

SC/ST category has the highest percentage of below average scores (21.9%). When education level is considered, it reveals that candidates with education levels above higher secondary have the highest percentage of above average scores (38.1 %), while secondary level candidates have the highest percentage of below average scores (39.1 %). The age-category distribution indicates that adult candidates have the highest percentage of above average scores (28.7 %), while teen-aged candidates have the highest percentage of below average scores (18.4%).

5.3 Statistical Tests for Proposed Hypotheses

Building upon the previously established covariates and the analysis techniques in Section 4, the independent samples ANOVA results reveal that social awareness within the studied population is significantly stratified across core demographic and spatial dimensions. Developmental maturity and gender play decisive roles in shaping civic comprehension; adult respondents consistently demonstrate superior social awareness compared to teenagers, while female participants exhibit a distinct advantage over their male counterparts. The observed phenomenon wherein female respondents exhibit significantly higher levels of social awareness may be partially attributed to the women-led educational initiatives implemented by Jana Sanskriti within the targeted regions of study. These individual-level differences are further compounded by geographic location and socio-cultural stratifications. Regional analyses indicate a pronounced spatial divide, identifying high-awareness clusters like Pathar Pratima and broader districts like South 24 Parganas, in stark contrast to lower-performing regions such as Puncha, Kulpi, and the Purulia district. Furthermore, the analysis reveals a significant disparity along racial lines, wherein respondents from the General category exhibit the highest levels of awareness, contrasted by the SC/ST demographic registering the lowest - suggesting distinct structural barriers to civic information for historically marginalized communities.

Educational attainment proves to be a critical determinant of social awareness. The analysis decisively rejects the null hypothesis for education level, indicating a robust, positive correlation between formal schooling and societal engagement. Post-hoc analyses confirm that individuals with an "Above Higher Secondary" education possess the highest mean social awareness scores within the sample, with mean differences being significantly greater than other groups. Conversely, those limited to "Pre-Secondary" education demonstrate the lowest overall scores. This linear progression underscores the indispensable role of advanced educational access in fostering comprehensive social consciousness.

Finally, religion emerges as the singular demographic variable examined that fails to yield a significant variance in social awareness, with a significance value observed at $p = 0.868$. However, the failure to reject the null hypothesis in this context must be interpreted with extreme methodological caution. Severe representational imbalances between the religious groups - specifically, a sample size of 386 for Hindus compared to only 20 for Muslims - heavily undermine the statistical reliability of this inter-faith comparison. This extreme disparity in sample sizes restricts the test's statistical power, rendering any definitive conclusions regarding the relationship between religion and social awareness premature without a more equitably distributed sample. To mitigate the severe sample size imbalance, an iterative stratified downsampling approach was employed, performing 1,000 independent Welch's t-tests between the minority demographic and randomly balanced subsets of the majority group. The aggregated results demonstrated a lack of statistical significance, yielding a median p-value of 0.6291, and only 0.70% of iterations falling in the $p < 0.05$ region. By correcting for the initial representational skew, these results strongly reinforce the conclusion that social awareness is not significantly differentiated by faith. We have uploaded all the statistical test results, deterministic cross tabulations and data files in the following github repository:
<https://github.com/Jackknife49/Statistical-Study-of-Young-Individuals-in-South-24-Parganas-and-Purulia>.

6 Discussion and Conclusion

[18] suggested that there is no significant disparity in social awareness across gender, stream of study (arts or science), and family status (joint or nuclear) in the Purba Medinipur district of West Bengal. However, our study claims that such differences, especially when it comes to gender, are present in the chosen regions of study from South 24 Parganas and Purulia. Their study also suggested that awareness levels among both genders are generally healthy. Both these observations could be supported by the fact that the general literacy rate as well as the male literacy rate in Purba Medinipur is much higher in comparison with both Purulia and South 24 Parganas.

Both the deterministic approach and the statistical tests revealed a significant difference in social awareness levels across several demographic categories, namely gender, race, age, education level, district, and block, with the sole exception of religion. Among the categories that exhibited significant differences, the groups demonstrating higher levels of social awareness were generally consistent with intuitive expectations. For instance, adults displayed greater awareness than adolescents, and individuals with higher educational attainment were more socially aware than those with lesser qualifications. Similarly, districts and blocks with a stronger legacy of literacy and welfare exhibited higher levels of social awareness compared to others. However, contrary to prevalent public perception, our statistical analysis did not indicate any significant difference in social awareness levels among the religious groups. This result may be attributable to imbalanced sample sizes across the religious categories; nevertheless, one should not dismiss the possibility that there may indeed be no substantial disparity in awareness levels among these populations.

Other studies like [17] and [16] found varying results with respect to gender, with [17] stating that the level of awareness about human rights among boys is slightly higher than that in girls, however, no such significant difference was found in [16], which measures awareness by reading habits. International studies like [13] and [14], based on South Africa and the USA respectively, did not find any significant difference among groups of gender or race in political or racial awareness. However, [13] did suggest that there is a significant difference across the year of study, meaning age and educational level do affect the level of awareness among individuals.

Social entrepreneurship is mostly in India confused with social work, hence it is unable to make a mark as an individual entity in India. This is starting of challenge for social entrepreneurship. However we consider social entrepreneurship to be a particularly exciting and fruitful research topic and it is our hope that this study and the corresponding initiatives will bring us a step closer toward legitimizing and inspiring social entrepreneurship as a means to create social and economic value and as a field of research. The outputs of the study will not only be useful from the perspective of social entrepreneurship, but also from the point of view of the policy-makers at any level. We recommend educating the groups with relatively low awareness, an effort that is advancing through the use of theatre and plays.

The results obtained from both the deterministic approach and statistical methods consistently indicate that the categorical variables significantly influence the social aware ness levels of the surveyed individuals, as measured through their standardized total scores. This agreement between methods reinforces the robustness of our findings.

Our analysis also reveals no significant disparity among the question blocks concerning social awareness. This suggests that there is no section of the study where relative awareness is alarmingly low, indicating a generally uniform level of social awareness across the different question categories.

We recommend targeting educational initiatives towards groups with relatively low awareness. Jana Sanskriti is actively working towards this goal through innovative approaches like theatre and plays, which can effectively convey messages and promote social awareness.

References

- [1] Rawal, T., 2018. A study of Social Entrepreneurship in India. *International Research Journal of Engineering and Technology*, 5(01), pp.70-95.
- [2] Mair, J. and Marti, I., 2006. Social entrepreneurship research: A source of explanation, prediction, and delight. *Journal of world business*, 41(1), pp.36-44.
- [3] Dees, J.G., 1998. *The Meaning of Social Entrepreneurship*. Kauffman Foundation and Stanford University.
- [4] Austin, J.E., Stevenson, H.H. and Wei-Skillern, J., 2003. Social entrepreneurship and commercial entrepreneurship: same, different, or both?. Division of Research, Harvard Business School.
- [5] Boschee, J., 1995. Social Entrepreneurship: Never thought that profit and philanthropy would go hand in hand?. *Across the board*, 32, pp.20-25.
- [6] Sagawa, S. and Segal, E., 2000. Common interest, common good: Creating value through business and social sector partnerships. *California management review*, 42(2), pp.105-122.
- [7] Waddock, S.A., 1988. Building successful social partnerships. *MIT Sloan Management Review*, 29(4), p.17.
- [8] Alvord, S.H., Brown, L.D. and Letts, C.W., 2004. Social entrepreneurship and societal transformation: An exploratory study. *The journal of applied behavioral science*, 40(3), pp.260-282.
- [9] Dees, J.G. and Anderson, B.B. (2003) Sector-Bending: Blurring Lines between Non-profit and For-Profit. *Society*, 40, 16-27.
- [10] Emerson, J. and Twersky, F. (1996) *New Social Entrepreneurs: The Success, Challenge, and Lessons of Non-Profit Enterprise Creation*. The Roberts Foundation, San Francisco.
- [11] Jones, DE, Greenberg, M and Crowley, M ; Early social-emotional functioning and public health: The relationship between kindergarten social competence and future wellness, *American Journal of Public Health*, e-View Ahead of Print, doi: 10.2105/AJPH.2015.302630
- [12] Huynh S.V ; Social Awareness and Responsible Decision Making of Students in Grade 4 and 5 in Vietnam *Journal of Education and Human Development* December 2018, Vol. 7, No. 4, pp. 7-15
- [13] Badaru, K. A. & Adu, E. O. (2021). The Political Awareness and Participation of University Students in post-Apartheid South Africa. *Research in Social Sciences and Technology*, 6(3), 1-24.
- [14] Aldana, A., Rowley, S. J., Checkoway, B., & Richards-Schuster, K. (2012). Raising Ethnic-Racial Consciousness: The Relationship Between Intergroup Dialogues and Adolescents' Ethnic-Racial Identity and Racism Awareness. *Equity & Excellence in Education*, 45(1), 120–137. <https://doi.org/10.1080/10665684.2012.641863>

- [15] Ahmad S., Dar B.A., Lone J.A. ; Reading Habits and Attitudes of Undergraduate Students: A Gender Based Comparative Study of Government Degree College (Boys) and Government Degree College for Women, Anantnag (J&K) ; Library Philosophy and Practice (e-journal) (2019), 2351
- [16] Binjha P.B.; Students' Awareness of Human Rights Education at Higher Secondary School level; International Journal of Social Science And Human Research (2022), 4746-4749
- [17] Begum D.; A comparative study on Perception of Human rights between male and female students at the undergraduate level.; Turkish Journal of Computer and Mathematics Education Vol.12 No.12 (2021), 3413-3416
- [18] Bera A.,Ashutosh S. ; Study of Social Awareness among School Students in Purba Medinipur District of West Bengal; Central Asian Journal Of Social Sciences And History Volume: 04 Issue: 05 — May 2023 (ISSN: 2660-6836) (ISSN: 2660-6836)

Appendix

Block-wise Category Distribution

Table 1: Block * Category Crosstabulation

District	Block	Above Average	Average	Below Average	Total
Purulia	Hura	3 (8.6%)	28 (80.0%)	4 (11.4%)	35 (100%)
	Puncha	9 (10.1%)	49 (55.1%)	31 (34.8%)	89 (100%)
South 24 Parganas	Kulpi	20 (19.4%)	69 (67.0%)	14 (13.6%)	103 (100%)
	Pathar Pratima	40 (22.6%)	118 (66.7%)	19 (10.7%)	177 (100%)
Total		72 (17.8%)	264 (65.3%)	68 (16.8%)	404 (100%)

District-wise Category Distribution

Table 2: District * Category Crosstabulation

District	Above Average	Average	Below Average	Total
Purulia	12 (9.7%)	77 (62.1%)	35 (28.2%)	124 (100.0%)
South 24 Parganas	60 (21.4%)	187 (66.8%)	33 (11.8%)	280 (100.0%)
Total	72 (17.8%)	264 (65.2%)	68 (16.8%)	405 (100.0%)

Religion-wise Category Distribution

Table 3: Religion * Category Crosstabulation

Religion	Above Average	Average	Below Average	Total
Hindu	66 (17.2%)	253 (65.9%)	65 (16.9%)	384 (100%)
Muslim	6 (30.0%)	11 (55.0%)	3 (15.0%)	20 (100%)
Total	72 (17.8%)	264 (65.3%)	68 (16.8%)	404 (100%)

Gender-wise Category Distribution

Table 4: Gender * Category Crosstabulation

Gender	Above Average	Average	Below Average	Total
Female	62 (20.9%)	200 (67.6%)	34 (11.5%)	296 (100%)
Male	10 (9.3%)	64 (59.3%)	34 (31.5%)	108 (100%)

Total	72 (17.8%)	264 (65.3%)	68 (16.8%)	404 (100%)
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Table 5: gender * category Crosstabulation (Purulia)

Gender	Above Average	Average	Below Average	Total
Female	8 (9.9%)	54 (66.7%)	19 (23.5%)	81 (100.0%)
Male	4 (9.3%)	23 (53.5%)	16 (37.2%)	43 (100.0%)
Total	12 (9.7%)	77 (62.1%)	35 (28.2%)	124 (100.0%)

Table 6: Gender * category Crosstabulation (south24parganas)

Gender	Above Average	Average	Below Average	Total
Female	54 (25.1%)	146 (67.9%)	15 (7.0%)	215 (100.0%)
Male	6 (9.2%)	41 (63.1%)	18 (27.7%)	65 (100.0%)
Total	60 (21.4%)	187 (66.8%)	33 (11.8%)	280 (100.0%)

Race-wise Category Distribution

Table 7: Race * Category Crosstabulation

Race	Above Average	Average	Below Average	Total
GEN	29 (22.8%)	85 (66.9%)	13 (10.2%)	127 (100%)
OBC	19 (18.8%)	66 (65.3%)	16 (15.8%)	101 (100%)
SC/ST	24 (13.6%)	113 (64.2%)	39 (22.2%)	176 (100%)
Total	72 (17.8%)	264 (65.3%)	68 (16.8%)	404 (100%)

Table 8: Race * category Crosstabulation (Purulia)

Race	Above Average	Average	Below Average	Total
GEN	3 (17.6%)	11 (64.7%)	3 (17.6%)	17 (100.0%)
OBC	4 (12.9%)	21 (67.7%)	6 (19.4%)	31 (100.0%)
SC/ST	5 (6.6%)	45 (59.2%)	26 (34.2%)	76 (100.0%)
Total	12 (9.7%)	77 (62.1%)	35 (28.2%)	124 (100.0%)

Table 9: Race * category Crosstabulation (south24parganas)

Race	Above Average	Average	Below Average	Total
GEN	26 (23.6%)	74 (67.3%)	10 (9.1%)	110 (100.0%)
OBC	15 (21.4%)	45 (64.3%)	10 (14.3%)	70 (100.0%)
SC/ST	19 (19.0%)	68 (68.0%)	13 (13.0%)	100 (100.0%)
Total	60 (21.4%)	187 (66.8%)	33 (11.8%)	280 (100.0%)

Education-wise Category Distribution

Table 10: Education * Category Crosstabulation

Class	Above Average	Average	Below Average	Total
Above HS	18 (40.0%)	23 (51.1%)	4 (8.9%)	45 (100%)
Higher Secondary	25 (19.7%)	88 (69.3%)	14 (11.0%)	127 (100%)
Secondary	21 (12.8%)	104 (63.4%)	39 (23.8%)	164 (100%)

Pre-secondary	8 (11.8%)	49 (72.1%)	11 (16.2%)	68 (100%)
Total	72 (17.8%)	264 (65.3%)	68 (16.8%)	404 (100%)

Table 11: Education * category Crosstabulation (Purulia)

Class	Above Average	Average	Below Average	Total
Above HS	8 (38.1%)	9 (42.9%)	4 (19.0%)	21 (100.0%)
Higher Secondary	2 (4.4%)	34 (75.6%)	9 (20.0%)	45 (100.0%)
Secondary	2 (4.3%)	26 (56.5%)	18 (39.1%)	46 (100.0%)
Presecondary	0 (0.0%)	8 (66.7%)	4 (33.3%)	12 (100.0%)
Total	12 (9.7%)	77 (62.1%)	35 (28.2%)	124 (100.0%)

Table 12: Education * category Crosstabulation (south24parganas)

Class	Above Average	Average	Below Average	Total
Above HS	10 (41.7%)	14 (58.3%)	0 (0.0%)	24 (100.0%)
Higher Secondary	23 (28.0%)	54 (65.9%)	5 (6.1%)	82 (100.0%)
Secondary	19 (16.1%)	78 (66.1%)	21 (17.8%)	118 (100.0%)
Presecondary	8 (14.3%)	41 (73.2%)	7 (12.5%)	56 (100.0%)
Total	60 (21.4%)	187 (66.8%)	33 (11.8%)	280 (100.0%)

Age-wise Category Distribution

Table 13: Age * Category Crosstabulation

Age	Above Average	Average	Below Average	Total
Adult	27 (28.7%)	56 (59.6%)	11 (11.7%)	94 (100%)
Teen-aged and Below	45 (14.5%)	208 (67.1%)	57 (18.4%)	310 (100%)
Total	72 (17.8%)	264 (65.3%)	68 (16.8%)	404 (100%)

Table 14: Age * category Crosstabulation (Purulia)

Age	Above Average	Average	Below Average	Total
Adult	9 (20.9%)	25 (58.1%)	9 (20.9%)	43 (100.0%)
Teen aged and below	3 (3.7%)	52 (64.2%)	26 (32.1%)	81 (100.0%)
Total	12 (9.7%)	77 (62.1%)	35 (28.2%)	124 (100.0%)

Table 15: Age * category Crosstabulation (south24parganas)

Age	Above Average	Average	Below Average	Total
Adult	18 (35.3%)	31 (60.8%)	2 (3.9%)	51 (100.0%)
Teen aged and below	41 (17.9%)	156 (68.4%)	31 (13.6%)	228 (100.0%)
Total	60 (21.4%)	187 (66.8%)	33 (11.8%)	280 (100.0%)